

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE PROFESSIONAL LIFE EXPERIENCES OF EDUCATIONAL OFFICERS IN DISTRICT SWAT

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ABSTRACT

In district Education set up, educational officers are the most important figure of the whole system. Because educational officers ensure supervision and administrative control over the system at district level. For good governance and service delivery in efficient and collaborative manner but despite all these services, the educational officers faces many uncertainty and different challenges in their professional lives which became a hurdle in their efficient performance and in this regard the researcher take interest to investigate into professional live experiences of educational officers in district swat. The study focused on main three significant research objectives such as investigation about the professional life experiences of educational officer, understanding about the challenges facing by educational officers during performance of their duties, and to highlight the demands and needs required for their professional development and enhancement of their skills in different areas of educational administration in District Swat. Moreover, over to investigate the professional life experiences of educational officers in district swat, the researcher formulated four main research questions for which the researcher followed a qualitative research design. To investigate further the researcher identified Population which comprised of female educational officers working in education department in district swat by means of purposive sampling techniques where sample group formed, consisted of 08 respondents for this research study and the data collected were analyzed through thematic analysis techniques for which all the six major steps of thematic analysis were followed. Findings of research study divulges that according to the views and experiences of these educational officers, they consider opportunities for the enhancement of their professional development, communication skills, trainings and workshops and leadership opposition and direct collaboration with different stakeholders are significant aspects of their professional lives. Result further reveals that there are some challenges in the shape of resources, staff deficiencies, lack of professional management trainings, Political pressures and interference of the stakeholders which undermine the performance and decision-making Power of the educational officers at district level. Based on the findings and result of the research study, professional trainings and workshops, coordination with the other districts I the field of educational administration and skilled staff availability and other facilities which enhance the professional growth of the educational officers were recommended.

Keywords: Professional Lives; Personal Development; Lack of Resources; District Educational Officers

INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the important features of educational institution in the whole world due to its significance and accomplishment of

the desired areas of the vision of educational institution. According to the research study of Islam, & Hussain, 2020, it guides, inspires,

and motivates all human, intellectual, and financial resources. According to Coleman and Briggs (2002) further highlights that, leadership involves persuading members of a group to achieve predetermined goals inside an organization. Research conducted by Gul, Malik, Juman, & Hussain, 2019, this methodical procedure adheres to both formal and informal means for inspiration, motivation, and communication.

According to the opinion of experts, action of educational administrator both in positive and adverse impact depending on the situation and circumstances. According to the views of Yeung, Ong, Davies, Gao, & Perkins, 2012, Hussain 2014, if it is observed that the administrative targets set were in line with expectations, they would likely receive positive reinforcement, and vice versa. Research study reveals that to meet educational goals it is authoritative that administrative procedures align with the institutional policies and theoretical framework which contributes positively to all the stakeholders involved in the process. At district level the educational officers being representative of the provincial government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, ensure to implementation of Government Policies, instructions and orders within their territorial jurisdiction. As per vision of Iqbal, it is the prime responsibilities of educational administrator to implement educational policies for the development and prosperity of society to meet the demand of the community. He defines education policy as a government policy that provides guidance for the execution of educational initiatives that directly and visibly impact the nation's institutions and populace. According to the Ministry of Education (MOE), 2015, P-88, the Provincial Departments of Education oversee managing elementary, secondary, technical, and post-secondary education as well as putting national education plans into practice.

It is obvious that teachers absenteeism and inadequate supervision are also impacted due to management practices of the education sector which affected the implementation of educational policies. In this regard the provincial government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa has more problems and hurdles

in the process of implementation which negatively impacted the process of putting the policies in action while educational officers at district level plays a crucial role in educational services in such like phenomena and carry out their administrative responsibilities. Some of the parameters of the departmental policies in this study are the theoretical framework provided to them in the form of a job description, rules and regulations, a code of ethics, and some administrative instructions. According to Mahmud and Iqbal (2018) resource management, office administration, policy implementation, and policy gap reduction at the district level. It was further highlighted that professional approach in different areas are required to educational officers for their professional growth. A variety of demands and requirements are necessary for the efficient management and advancement of education systems at the district level, according to district education officials. These criteria and needs fall into a few categories:

To stay abreast of the most recent developments in educational trends, policies, and management techniques, district education officials require ongoing professional development. It is essential to have training programs in curriculum development, data administration, leadership, monitoring and evaluation (Nazak, Asghar., & Javed, 2019; Saleem, & Saeed, 2021). It is crucial to have access to sufficient material, human, and financial resources. This covers the cost of maintaining well-maintained facilities, educational resources, and schools. It is also essential to have the right communication tools and office infrastructure. Effective and transparent channels of communication are essential for external stakeholders as well as within the educational system. This comprises ICT platforms and tools for consistent reporting, feedback, and updates. Monitoring and assessing educational programs and school performance requires the use of efficient instruments and procedures. Systems for gathering data, analytical instruments, and instruction in data interpretation (Yeung, Ong, Davies, Gao, & Perkins, 2012).

Throughout their job, district education officers face a number of obstacles, such as inadequate levels of capacity building at the district level and a lack of accountability for their responsibilities at the directorate and district levels, issues brought about by local governments, political pressure and departmental pressure at their level, lack of working relationship with district governments, and lack of required tools for assessing the extent to which policies have been implemented (Mahmud & Iqbal, 2018). District education officials' needs and requirements are divided into categories based on competencies. One such competency is technical, which is characterized by a consistent ability to recognize the essential elements of any given problem, apply one's own technical expertise to solve it, and assess solutions in light of that expertise. using well-known computer programs to acquire as much data as possible prior to making a choice (Shah, 2009).

It is obvious that education generally recognized a foundation for the welfare and development of the community, Cultural progress and its transmission to the next generation, societal and economic growth of the region. Due to education the inhabitants of the region became aware about their fundamental rights and their role in the society whereof the Educational Officers plays a significant role in functioning of their performance within the education frame work and particularly in district swat. The educational officers are the representatives of the Provincial government to execute the education policies and ensure its implementation, supervising and Monitoring schools and nurturing an environment, feasible for learning which need the needs and demands of the students as well as the community.

For district education officials to properly administer and enhance local educational systems, these demands and prerequisites are essential. Taking care of these areas from the South African government has made improving teaching and learning in schools one of its top priorities. According to Paolini (2015) the biggest difficulty is raising the standard of instruction in classrooms and,

more especially, raising learning outcomes. In order to provide high-quality instruction, efficient evaluation, improved student performance, and achievement, school district offices are essential. Given the important role and support that school districts provide to schools, the school district offices play an important role in facilitating the desired educational transformation as mediators between schools and the government (Moososi, Bantwini, Molale, & Diko, 2020; Jenkins, 2019). It is essential that they possess the ability to support and resolve issues that schools face. According to Bantwini, and King-McKenzie (2011) there are several issues facing school districts, one of which is a human capacity shortage that makes it difficult for the few authorities to provide efficient support to teachers and schools.

Additionally, the professional life experiences of these educational officers include their role, responsibilities, challenges faced by them during performance their duty, their financial needs, professional development requirements, and leadership style are the areas which will be explored due to this research study. This research study intended to cover the gaps by investigating the lived experiences of educational officers

Education Officers deals with the management, supervision and reporting of educational matters to the concerned authority. They have significant contribution in uplifting the Quality /Standard of Education. However, their professional lives, associated Challenges and issues are not explored which negatively impact them in the shape of unrealistic expectation from all the stakeholders. Studies revealed that they are overburden (overloaded workload) Professional stress Job (Station) insecurity, Political Pressure and above all less opportunity for their professional development which negatively affect the professional lives, therefore, this study will explore the professional lives of District Education officers with the purpose to orient all the selected stakeholders about their professional lives and their Problems and ensure their Professional opportunities etc.

Educational officers play a role of bridge and a representative of provincial government for

the implementation and execution of national and international level policies at grassroots level. The ability and professional development of educational officers has a great impact on the development and improvement of educational institutions as well as the employee's capacity building but due to some challenges and barriers their performance and efficacy has been affected. This study will point out their needs and requirement for professional development which increases their capacity for the enhancement of supportive mechanism which lead towards the improvement in educational outcomes.

Educational officers have a significant role in manipulating the quality and effectiveness of education at district level and plays a pivotal role which serves as reason for this research study. It is necessary to understand the lived experiences of these educational officers in district swat where educational environment has been molded due to numerous reasons including socio political and economic factors. such as challenges faced by them, external pressure of the elites and in sufficient allocation of funds etc. This study will explore these hinderances and highlights the strategies for their improvement.

Educational officers are the in charge of the overall school monitoring and supervision and administration and has a significant role in the effectiveness and quality education at district level. Moreover, the educational officers (Eos) play a pivotal role in the implementation of educational policies of provincial government at district level but despite the facts of their significant role, they face numerous challenges and difficulties which hindrances in their efficient performance and affect their professional life such as insufficient resources, lack of facilities, building infrastructure and political interference in their official business and inadequate professional trainings.

The study aims to explore the best practices which improved the lived experiences of the educational officers to provide opportunity to ensure conducive environment for leaning which meet the needs of the society and the students. Institutional growth and community

involvement lead towards quality education which improve the socio-economic situation and political instability in the region and thereby educational officers' role is imperative in this regard. This research study will fill the gaps and provide strategies for further research to overcome deficiencies and improved the lived experiences of educational officers in district swat for better management and changes in the educational frame work.in conclusion this research study will contribute to develop a more inclusive ad supportive environment to educational officers for their improvement and professional development. Research study investigates that because of the scarcity of resources and understanding towards role & responsibilities, Professional trainings and skills which resulted challenges faced by educational officers, create hurdles to support them and improve their professional life experiences. Research study conducted by various scholars and educationist reveals that in such like circumstances teaching learning process and performance of educational officers are badly affected which ultimately undermine the result of student's outcomes which lead towards the insurgency of educational system at district level and due to which educational policies and instructions of the Provincial government could not be implemented accordingly. This research study will enable the scholar to address these issues by investigating the professional life experiences of educational officers with the aim to investigate and examine the factors which affects their performance and became hurdle for conducive environment of learning and will also provide a plan to ensure improvement in their professional lives for the quality education which meet the needs of the society at district level.

Review Of Literature

The literature review determines the practices adopted by educational officers in their daily routine practice pertaining to their professional development and official business and re-examined by means of a particular parameter and compare it with their observation and experiences and knowledge with the instructive conclusion., which affected their performance and efficiency. The

research study emphasizes on the daily performance and observation made by the educational officers regarding their role and responsibilities as compared to their performance with challenges faced by them at district level. These observations and challenges faced by them are very significant for the enhancement of their professional growth and advancement of educational system to ensure the achievements of objectives for better planning and management to enhance their performance to meet the demands of students as well as the community.

The examination of experienced life facts amongst educational administrators' officers divulges miscellaneous perceptions into their occupation paths, encounters, and growth. Numerous research studies identify the importance of the factors which affect the professional and personal life of the educational officers due to these practices, such as leadership interaction, institutional management, provision of basic facilities, inadequate atmosphere etc. The educational officers at district level, facing problems and facing challenges in terms of the performing of their duty but they continue their efforts for the advancement of education and institutional growth good governance and service delivery to address the needs and requirements of the community.

Moreover, the review highlighted and identified the reasons behind these experiences such as institutional environment, components related to gender, management and supervision, challenges, behavior and interference of the political leaders and bureaucratic behavior and their attitude which

The research study by Baden, (2001) visit on the basis of his research that the educational district officers which plays the role of district administrator is wholly responsible on various areas because of this the quality education has gone pathetic in addition to their experiences in their professional life. These things became issues and problems in the context of financial management, management in the office, resources, developing an institution and good management which led to fairness and decision in relation to the prevailing rules and

laws of the country. The research establishes the educational officers (Eos) as highly dedicated and faithful to their profession regardless of the realities concerning constraints, non-community support and mounting pressure to provide quality education. Further, the district educational officers are a designated agent /representative of the provincial Government of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa in the performance of the orders, policies and decision in its territorial jurisdiction and thus, they are developing obstacles and hindrances in the enforcement of rules and laws in the practical life of the profession.

Research study in intents and purposes brings out the professional and skillful opinion of the researchers who already work hard and emphasize their role, their duties and their Job description (JDs) and their effective contribution in the grow of the institution and the implementation of the administration policies in the area of the study and to further achieve the educational goals and objectives. Based on the many research studies, it has established that the district educational officer who is the district educational administrator plays a major role in the educational setting in the education frame work. The educational administrator performance acts as an adjudicator between the institutions of district level and the Government in the professional life. Role of district educational administrator is highly necessary in planning and management, assessment & evaluation, determination of the assignment and resolution of the issues in the form of decision and in implementation of the orders and Policies of the Government at district level. In this Chapter, which is a literature review, the central theme led to perception and concept of educational administration, significance of educational administration, various theories revolving around administration, roles of district educational officers, and the challenges encountered in their career life (Coleman & Briggs, 2002).

The reading of the experience of the professional life of the education officers at district portrays big futures into the position and the challenges. The application is essential in the organization of educational

institution in order to limit these difficulties and challenges that the officers face during the performance of their duties. Educational officers are significant when it comes to educational institutions and planning strategies within a district. Precisely, educational officers hold a statistically significant position at district level as assembled thought in education plans at education institutions. (Lane, R. J., Bishop, H. L. and Wilson-Jones, L. (2005). Besides their role and duty is quite significant in the support and coordination of acquisition of institutional development and capacity increase of employment to ensure implementation of the policy and its being executed in even the educational scene to complement the demand of the society with regard to efficient management. Yaro, I., Arshad, R., and Salleh, D. (2017).

Their management skills, professional development, education and other competencies in the profession of education positively impact their professional life experiences as an educational officer. The analysis of their lived experiences suggests further courses of action and planning necessary to combat these issues and implement effective strategies to meet the desired educational results since educational officers encounter numerous challenges in the form of budget, resources, infrastructure, facilities and other parameters affecting their professional lives. It is important to understand these challenges so as to design specific interventions and support system. District level in Swat is the major task highlighted in this chapter (Istakri, D., Sofyan, H.,2024). Roles, as well as responsibilities are fundamental; managerial planning and strategies; operations activities and solutions to many challenges and problems. This research study echoed planning and implementation of policies and adherence to the rules and instructions by the district educational officers on the ground within the educational setting. The obstacles and hindrances encountered in posting / transfer, decision making, policy implementation, inadequate resources, budgeting, social constraints, environment and other influences by the district educational officers

whilst in striking duty will also be outlined in this research study.

Welfare and development of a society and a nation towards is greatly contributed by education. It goes without saying that through research work on earth all the world re-focusing and concentrating on the significance of education as well as educational officers play significant role in the development and promotion of education in any society, but it is also a fact that education officers are bogged down by numerous difficulties in their endeavors towards quality education in district Swat. The Swat state was established in 1915 and by the time the state emerged it was a model state and the centre of quality education keeping in view the role that the Ex-Ruler of Swat played in the significance of education, the 1st school was established in the capital city of Swat known as Saidu Sharif Swat the former state in 1922 which is the reason why many other schools were establish both male and female in Swat. The District Swat is located in the Province of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa whereby the environment was established to enable improved education due to strong and motivated culture, developed by the Ex-Ruler of Swat. Being in such like an environment, the educational officer, the then called District Inspector of Schools passing the same services without fear, threat and challenges. As the days progressed, the Swat district was severely overwhelmed by the Talibanization of Talibanization, a slightly plague that derailed the work of Education officer and eventually disrupted the climate of the educational situation, Uddin, J.(2022) Anglo Vernacular School (Wadudia School).

The swat District of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KP) has a lousy past education with numerous problems that eventually made impacts on the entire organization process, social and political environment and equally educational activities. The regionality of educational landscape requires development measures that ensure professional growth of education officers who have critical role in the fostering of education within the society such as Swat and specifically women education. The situation that creates the facts and circumstances on the progress of educational attainment to the women, is that Despite all the means created during the

occasion due to unacceptable situation and environment developed in the region, the teaching learning process and even the rate of learning is also hit and the District Educational Officers with all the means and dedication in work become to confront numerous challenges and difficulties in monitoring and supervision of the schooling going on. Khan, S. U., Khalid, A., and Elahi, N. 2020).

In the absence of harmony before the early 2000, harmony among the stakeholders and the educational administration was there and the Swat district was in Progress and leading the top position in regards to various benchmarks and indicators like enrollment, attendance, administrative visits, constructional and developmental work and other variables that contributes to the quality and access of education and promotes their integrity, professional route and growth in their own lived situations. It goes without saying that in the confusion in which the girls were not in a position to access education and they are the ones getting educated by the educational institutes since the entire system of education was not properly in order and yet the education officers toiling and trying to establish the quality education and improvement of education. Many educational institutions located in swat, providing, and administering education on the one hand at standard levels according to the needs of the community and the growth and prosperity of the institutions, but on the other hand, terrorists destroyed the institutions and caused uncertainty throughout the district swat as a result of which school was closed and remained non-functional and consequently not only a quality education was ravaged but also access and opportunities to get education. The importance of local community leadership in the process of reforms in education to restore the past condition of schooling and infrastructure is unavoidable which cannot be ignored .To rehabilitate these institutes and functionality of schools in the swat district conflicted area, effective strategies and planning for the future generation in terms of reforms regarding the restoration of the previous educational environment, the role and experiences of the educational officers and their focusses on education reform could not be ignored (Khan and Ali, 2021).

Swat district considered as a peace of land in Pakistan and was top District swat is situated within the boundaries of North of Pakistan and was a top in education but unfortunately it was the entire system and infrastructure was changed due to militants, political issues and uncertain Nity in the past decades due to which the survival and livelihood was in danger. The Govt; writ became very weak due to these revolts because they controlled over the whole swat in their hold by force due to which education machinery was not in its position and educational officers could not perform their duties accordingly and institutions were destroyed. This situation badly affected the little kids from their basic right of getting education because there were no accessibility and opportunity to institution. The whole district swat was in the control of the militant and there were insurgency and they were influenced over the whole system of the district and all the institutions including education were paralyzed. In such like circumstances, educational officer makes efforts for to rebuild the institution and motivate the community to encourage their students for institutional development and its functionalization which divulges the professional and lived experiences of educational officers To rebuild the institution and encourage students and community. According to research study conducted by Ahmed & Khan, 2022, educational officers at district level make efforts for the institutional development and re-establishment which reflected their professional and lived experiences.

It is obvious from the efforts of educational; officers at district level that educational institutions were rebuilt ,confidence developed in the community and students ,raise moral of the teachers which lead towards the re-set up of the educational institution and its development despite the challenges faced by the educational officers which enhanced the quality education .research study reveals that it is admitted facts that due to uncertainty and insurgency in the area where no one was safe and the whole machinery of the government were paralyzed which resulted high dropout rate of the

students but the educational officers continue their efforts and restore confidence of the students and moral of teachers.

Educational administration at district level has an important role in the assuring of good governance, transparency and accountability as well as in service delivery for the social, educational and welfare development of the community. literature review further highlights that policy implementation, decision making and instructions issued by Government, the role of educational officers cannot be ignored because the educational officer is a representative of the government at district level for the Purpose to meet the demand of the community and students to enhance quality education for the development and prosperity and welfare of the community. Role of educational officers at district level for effective management and supervision is crucial in the development of teacher's capacity building, effective teaching learning process, character building of the students and achievements of educational and world millennium development goals. Research conducted by Yadav,2022 which highlighted that instructive management in terms of educational administration is related to the management of any planned group of society or institution, as well as the founder of the educational institution. Research further divulges that effective teaching learning depends upon the strong administration and effective management as stated by Yadav, 2021.

Literature review and investigation reveals that educational officers have a significant role in the effective administration in the education system and in quality education at district level but despite the facts and figure, there are many challenges which in the shape of resources, outside pressure in decision making and infrastructure which affect the performance of the educational officers and undermine the institutional growth and confidence of the community. Similarly, such like situation has great impact on the smooth running of the institutions which ultimately affect the educational objectives due to which it became hurdle for effective implementation of government policies in educational system.

Shortage of teacher as per student's teacher rations, inadequate infrastructures and resources, work load on teachers are the aspects which affect the performance of the educational officers and their professional development; therefore, it is essentials to make better planning and develop strategy for professional development of the educational officers which will lead towards the improvement in teaching learning and will enhance teacher capacity in their different areas of improvement. Keeping in view these aspects, the educational officers make efforts ensure proper procedures and methodology to enhance quality education to meet the demands of the community for their welfare and development.

During the investigation and literature review, it was transpired that infrastructure and other components has a pivotal role in the educational administration and management because learning activities, policy implementation and quality education are carried out but due to some challenges the desired goals could not be achieved according to the planned targets. According to the study conducted by Shamsul et al. ,2024, educational institutions without adequate facilities and building infrastructure could create conducive environment for learning. research studies confirm that infrastructure and facilities have a significant impact in success of education process in the institution.

The study investigates that professional life experiences of educational officer (EOs) at district level in district Swat is surrounded by various hurdles in the shape of challenges which affect the ability, performance and their efficiency for effective management and string educational system. These challenges, arising from structural, administrative, and personal factors, can significantly impact their roles in planning, managing, and delivering education. Research further highlights that there are some barriers in terms of weak administration, outside influence in decision making, scarcity of resources, gaps in learning and capacities, socio-political interference, and personal well-being. One of the biggest challenges faced by EOs in Swat district is directing the multifaceted administrative structure. The dual control system, where educational officers often report to both district and provincial authorities, leads

to uncertainties in roles and responsibilities. This intersection of authority not only leads to inefficiency but also weakens the independence of EOs in the decision-making process which resulted Poor performance and low-quality education and loses confidence of the community.

Basic facilities in the institutions have a great challenge and problem for educational officers at district level because many schools have lack of resources, basic facilities such as functional classrooms, clean drinking water, and proper sanitation conditions. Moreover, beside the others lack of teaching staff and educational resources weakens the problem, forcing the EO to seek alternative solutions to keep the schools functioning. Another element ie financial limitations also delay the ability of educational officials to efficiently implement planned programs. Budget allocations for education in the district are often insufficient, as funds are lacking to meet urgent needs such as infrastructure development, teacher training, and scientific combination. While the educational officers within their territorial Jurisdiction at district level make efforts and struggle to ensure reasonable access to quality education in schools to meet the needs of the students and demands of the community for better environment for social, ethical and economic development.

Socio-Political dynamics in the Swat district is a great problem for education uniformity because Political interference in recruitment, transfer, and promotion undermines merit policy and creates an atmosphere of nepotism and disbelief. There are pressure on educational officer by influential individuals who prioritize personal interests over institutional goals, which weakens the quality of education. Moreover, cultural norms and societal expectations sometimes contradict progressive educational policies. Resistance to girls' education at district level in district swat, puts EOs in difficult positions as they need to reconcile support for inclusive education with respect for local traditions. This tension not only undermines their professional autonomy but also complicates the implementation of gender-sensitive policies which became a hurdle for effective management and

administration and ultimately undermine the ability of the educational officers.

Literature review and investigation of the study divulges that the ability and efficiency of educational officers are subject to numerous challenges that impair to provide quality education. Overcoming these challenges requires a multi-faceted approach, including streamlining administrative processes, ensuring proper resource allocation, providing targeted training, minimizing political interference, and promoting well-being. Creating a supportive environment and equipping EOs with the necessary tools will allow the educational system in Swat district to unlock its full potential and contribute to sustainable development in their professional journey.

The research study under the research topic " An Investigation into the Professional Life Experiences of Educational Officers in District Swat" offers valuable considerations into the challenges and restrictions faced by educational officers in a particular socio-cultural background. In broader sense, this research study is very significant for the understanding inferences of educational leadership in Pakistan, specifically against the contextual background of reforms in decentralization structure. According to the research study conducted by Komatsu,2012, Educational institution employees in district Swat direct complex accountability frameworks influenced by local traditions, gender roles, and political pressures. Further the study conducted by Khan,2013 which reveals that most of the educational officers expressed their concern over the lack of capacity building workshops regarding office management, Planning & Development and financial management because due to these necessary components make hurdles in their effectiveness in leadership role. On the contrary, although the research highlights the difficulties faced by educational officers, it also suggests that these experiences can contribute to the development of elasticity and innovation in leadership practices, which could possibly lead to enhanced educational conclusions in the district which badly affects teaching leaning process and also impact on quality education.

The analysis of professional life situations of the given educational officers in Swat district reveals valuable facts about their activities and issues. Such officers are instrumental in educational leadership, which helps these institutions to reach their destined goals under the challenges that are specific to them like resource constraint and sociocultural barriers. The professional growth of these people is vital to ensure the enhancement of their qualification which directly has a bearing in the management and administration of schools. Furthermore, their experience is extremely important in the context of educational policies implementation. Through the review of these facets, the paper is expected to find answers to specific interventions, which can be used to help the educational officers (EOs) perform with enhanced success, eventually resulting in better education outcomes in the district. This offers important insights on the navigation of EOs through their duties amidst a context that is distinctive in terms of sociocultural context and resource constraint

The literature review of the research topic of the research work, that is, Study of the Professional life experience of the educational officers in Swat district, gives enough knowledge on the roles, challenges, training requirements, well being, leadership styles and wider implication of educational reforms of the educational officers. The literature underlines that EOs have an important role to play in the successful delivery of education policymaking, overseeing the efficiency of school work and assisting the teaching staff. They sometimes play supervisory, administrative control or itself as bridge between schools and higher educational authorities. Nonetheless, job descriptions and overlapping duties usually cause a lot of confusion lowering productivity.

Included in these challenges are factors such as: Administrative overload and overly complicated bureaucratic systems are a huge distraction to developmental activities, Scarcity of resources, facilities, and technological equipment does not allow educational officers to carry out their work effectively, Political influence and interference competes with their capacity to judgment, as

well as create conflicts of interest, especially in places such as Swat District, Dar-ul-uloom, and other cultural practices interfere with the process of reforming the education. According to most of the studies, what stands out is the absence of quality and pertinent professional development programs that suit the needs of the EOs. The infrequent, situation-specific training constrains their capability to be responsive to altering training needs and it is slowing the Implementation of new practices.

The literature review can reveal the richness of the experience of EO and reveal that the system has to be improved in numerous ways. The most important recommendations are to improve the workload situation, arrange regular and specific training support, encourage constructive leadership, and have sufficient resources. Researchers must advance their investigations in the social, cultural direction and search the methods of new approaches to improve the life level and development of EOs in such areas like Swat District.

Major Objectives of the Study.

Keeping in view the nature of the study, the researcher developed the following research objectives ;

- I. To explore the Professional life experiences of Educational Officers (EOs) in District Swat.
- II. To find out the challenges faced by EOs while performing their duties in District Swat.
- III. To Explore the professional development needs and demands of EOs in District Swat.

Research methodology.

A qualitative method of research will be used to examine the career of the education officers in Swat District of Khyber Pakhtunkhwan. The study will be undertaken using a qualitative methodology; the whole management cadres of DEO, DDO, ADEO, SDEO, ASDEO will be used to select all the officials. These comprise all the district offices and tehsils of the district Swat of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. These participants of the study are employed as Tehsil and District Level management officers.

In the present study, the researcher will be conducting a qualitative study to examine the professional lives of the education officers in Swat District, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The qualitative approach will involve conducting the study by using all officials who are chosen among the management cadres of DEO, DDO, ADEO, SDEO, and ASDEO. These consist of all the district and tehsil offices of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa district Swat. These participants are staffing in the role of management officers on Tehsil and District Level.

The data gathered using open-ended interviews is to be analyzed using the methods of thematic analysis. Braun and Clarke (2006) identify six fundamental steps to follow in techniques of thematic analysis.

1. Familiarity with the data
2. Formulation of Code
3. Generating themes
4. Reviewing themes
5. Naming and defining themes
6. Discussions on themes

The steps will allow the researcher to address the research questions and it will allow the researcher to present conclusion regarding the study findings.

With this consideration of the professional life experience of the educational officers in district swat, researcher included the 08-education administrator as the respondents to the present research study population. Such respondents were; District Education Officer (DEO), Dy; District Education Officer (Dy;DEO) Sub divisional education Officer (SDEO) as well as Assistant Sub Divisional Education Officer (ASDEO). These education officers 08 were consulted and these education officers interviewed using self-developed interview questions.

In the case, 08 education Officers had been selected based on their experiences in professional life in terms of their role and responsibilities, Challenges they face in their performing in district swat with perspectives and experiences in their professional life. Education Officers has been chosen among the district as well as tehsil level to gather data that will be analyzed in the present research study. In addition, self-constructed interview

questions were controlled and served the 08 sampled respondents as population of the study where data and other response rate of the educational officers were 100% satisfactory and in such a fashion data were gathered to be analyzed.

Result & Discussion

As reflected in the responses of the respondents, one can argue that gender specific challenges in Professional role in Pashtun society are extremely problematic when it comes to female education officers and conversely there are societal barriers that create obstacles to female education officers but to alleviate those issues there should be awareness campaign, advocacy and atmosphere that empower female education officers in their role without external pressure and this will provide pleasant environment which enhances quality education.

The research revealed that the educational officers possess immense influence and impact on the significant leadership role in the determination of the teacher's recruitment, budget allocation, staff training and implementation of policies. Educational officers have a very great influence in customizing the policies as pointed out by Leithwood and Seashore-Louis, 2012. Besides, the study further indicated the due to the strong position, educational officers have quality of leadership and play an important role, hence it improves the performance of education officers to meet different stakeholders to improve the education quality. This part of the education officer brings to fore their important role in establishing policies and cover the educational reforms (Hargreaves & Fullan, 2012).

Revealed through the discovery of the finding is that educational officers because of their dynamic role in the professional development, have advanced in other areas of professional growth namely self-confidence, communication skills, decision making, and in leadership skills and are continually involved with various stakeholders to address various needs of the education management. The research study indicated that advisory development and personal growth can lead to the amelioration of the Coordination in organization and efficiency and interaction with stakeholders to guarantee

quality education and institutional growth (Day and Sammons, 2013).

External pressure has negatively influenced the lives of the educational officers in one way or another such as challenges in different forms such as societal hinderances, politicians' interference, No support from department and gender inequality etc. researched study by Fullen, 2011, showed that the problem solving and execution of the educational reforms and policies is negatively influenced due to external pressure in one way or another.

The study specifies that because of the office politics, the grouping in the offices, shortage of funds and shortage of human resources in comparison to their work, the ability and performance of the educational offices is significantly affected negatively, thus creating an environment where trust, confidence and relationship are destabilized and trimming down collaboration, coordination among the employees in the organization (Hanushek & Woessmam, 2020). The results through the prism of the research study, revealed that to attain educational aims and illuminating the human resource performance, human resource planning is essential (Baker, 2019).

The result of the study disclosed that the female educational offices in Pashtun society suffer a lot in the process of conducting their duty which makes their professional autonomy and performance ineffective. Their performance in such a case depends on the factors, which include the lack of family support, restrictions within their community, gender inequality, and inadequate power in decision making. The research study suggests that gender discrimination and prejudices in the organization will diminish the potential participation and involvement of female leaders and will undermine their advancement in the educational setting. (Lynch et al, 2020). Further it has been emphasized in the research study that the respondents emphasized on systemic support to enable female educational officers to attain sustainable development goals related to the education and gender equality (World Bank, 2018).

As noted during a research study of the findings, staff shortage and the workload forcing the educational officers to change the task assigned to them without their jurisdiction

that lead to inefficiency, management, and mismanagement of the team, which results in mental stress and agony on the team. Research also revealed that effective and appropriate human resources are crucial in actual and successful service provision and eliminate psychological strain among the educational officers (Baker, 2019). The analysis of the discovery through the prism of the earlier literature revealed that the shortage of resources compromises the power of educational officers that influence their performance, thereby reducing the impact of the quality governance and learning outcomes (Hanushek & Woessmann, 2020).

The results discuss that the educational officers experiencing critical situation in form of Challenges of political elites and community hurdles inhibiting their performance. The paper further identifies that strategic planning is essential to enable the education officer to avoid political influence in decision making besides posting transfer. Besides, performance of educational officers is also hampered by local traditions and constraints on resources when executing the duty. Research study also point out that when politicians interfere with the business of the educational administration, then the institutional sovereignty and in policy implementation is depreciated (Farooq & Saeed, 2018). The researcher found out that the educational officers were limited to the societal norms and local traditions which did not permit the officers to conduct extensive and reasonable educational activities. In the same way, the political interference by the political leaders discourages the power of the educational officers and the firmness of the management as well as the merit base decision is disrupted.

The study focused on the importance of the capacity building and skill development for the development of the educational officer's performance, ability and efficiency within the educational frame work. Respondents during the investigation also highlighted that professional development programs are the backbone of the officers due to which their moral, efficiency and capability are enhanced. Capacity building and skill development programs nurtures the administrative and managerial qualities and empowering the

educational officers for effective implementation and execution of policies for administrative change and educational reforms. (Fullan,2020). Study further highlighted that the capacity and skill development programs equip the educational officers for their professional development, better planning and decision making which has a great impression on the authority of organizational stability and discipline (Darling-Hammond et al, 2017).

To empower the educational officers in their professional life for effective decision and operation of assigning task with the educational frame work according to the policies, skill development programs are essential for their effective role as the same has been highlighted in the study of finding. As the role of educational officer is vital in the execution of policies and promulgation of Government instruction at district level, they face various tasks which required balance and technical knowledge and interactive skills for becoming an effective leadership qualities. Research conducted by Bush & Glovers,2019, training on leadership for educational officers are very essentials because it stressed on planning, reconciliation in during conflicts and management for resources meaningfully enhance the performance of the organization as well the educational officers.

The finding of the responses indicates that to become effective female leaders, the essentials such as self-assurance, will power and flexibility are pivotal for their empowerment and effective management but the local traditions and cultural obstructed their performance due which their professional autonomy undermine and the resultantly quality education cannot be improved. This Phenomenon also affect their professional growth and leadership qualities in their professional life. According to Catalyst,2020, policy pertaining to gender sensitivity, mentorship program and institutional practices are essentials for the development of female leadership. The study further revealed that despite the qualities which the female leaders in educational environment possess but they serious hurdles which endanger their professional growth and competencies. It has also been observed through research study that women are mostly deprived from their promotion, and professional recognition due to

societal barriers. According to Catalyst (2020), female have less contact to important counsellor and mentor who are the supporter of their professional occupation.

The study of the responses of the respondents reveals that balancing Personal and professional life for educational officer is crucial because due to this aspect, moral and efficiency of the educational officers can be enhanced for which specific trainings, confidence willpower and logistic support are essentials within the educational environment as well as community. Further the study highlighted that that lack of facilitation and support may cause of frustration and minimized the interaction with the surrounding. female education officers sometimes face extra pressure from community which interference in balancing their life both personal and professional (Eagly and Carli,2007) Moreover balancing of personal and professional life of the educational officer is a challenge because their duties and responsibilities encompasses out of range and their jurisdiction which involve decision making, management related issues and task.

The study indicates that female educational officer faces many challenges due to which their performance is badly affected such as societal barriers, lack of encouragement t from families and departments and inadequate professional independence. These challenges prevent them for their effective role in the society as well as in education. According to Sultana,2015, in Pashtun society, female is mostly deprived from the opportunity of their professional authority and opportunity for their facilitations. Moreover, gender biases and inequality also the factors which affecting the role of the female education officer in this male dominant society. The respondents stressed on special training and policy changes for the empowerment female leaders and educational officer. According to world Economic Forum (2021) women are mostly deprived from their professional development in educational empowerment and leadership than their male colleagues. The lack of family support as well as societal encouragement cause of mental agony and affecting their efficiency and professional career (Tremblay,2020)

Conclusions

It was concluded that the role of the education officer is very significant because of collaboration and liaison with different stakeholders of the community which enhances their professional growth. Moreover, the findings also highlighted that educational officer has a pivotal role in the implementation of policies being representative of the Provincial government. beside professional growth, different trainings and programs enhances their role and effectiveness which has a great impact over the quality education.

The findings further revealed that educational officers face series of challenges which negatively affect their professional experiences and management. Moreover, external pressure in the shape of political interference, societal hurdles, and lack of departmental and family support affect the performance and ability of the education officers in their professional life experiences. findings and discussion further highlighted that opportunities for engagement of educational officers with different stakeholders and training session will overcome these obstacles which will improve not only quality education but also professional career and empowerment of female education officers.

Professional autonomy and efficiency of the educational officers affected due to lack of resources such as financial, transportation, security and noninvolvement in decision making in administrative matters and also nonsupport of the community. Moreover, over political interference & bureaucrats pressure destabilize the role and authority of the educational officer which affect the educational outcomes and impacted the professional life experiences of educational officers.

It is evident from the discussion and finding of the data analysis that for effective management, strong administrative decision, different programs and skills development are essential for the professional growth, confidence, balancing of personal & professional life as well as for the enhancement of the educational officers. Female educational officers need self-confidence, willpower and flexibility and

courage for their professional career but due to political instability and extra interference in the official matters and community insecurity and lack of support, their performance badly affected which resultantly destabilize their role in the community as well as within the education frame work.

Suggestions.

On the basis of thematic analysis and findings of the data gathered from the responses of the respondents and objectives of the research study, the following suggestions are made;

1. Training for Educational Officers in different areas related to their job and effective management, may be arranged. Which enhance their professional growth and development.
2. To implement educational policies and rule of law, the educational officers may be empowered in making decision.
3. Outside interference through political leaders may be banned regarding decision and policy implementation by educational officers so that educational officer effectively utilize their efforts within the educational frame work.
4. To make arrangement for special initiatives of training and workshops and advocacy campaign for stakeholders and politicians to avoid interference in decision making of the educational officers in Posting transfer and other administrative matters as well as societal barriers for smooth office business.
5. Ensure sufficient Human resources, mechanism to lessen the office politics and grouping and encourage performance-based promotion to ensure competency of the educational officers in the implementation of government instructions and by laws of the department.
6. Capacity building and skills development programs should be arranged for the professional growth and development of educational officers to enhance their moral and performance.

7. To encourage and support female educational officer, special initiatives should be taken to enhance the performance and moral of the female education officer for their empowerment, wellbeing and their role in the society which discourage inequality and discrimination and ensure balancing of their personal and professional life.

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